

GOVERNMENTAL SYSTEM AND FORM OF ADMINISTRATION OF AMIR TEMUR'S STATE

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If every citizen of Uzbekistan learns the history of our motherland free from objective and ideological views from scientific research works based on innovative approaches and makes good use of the results of such research in history education, our noble intentions and great goals - the "Third Renaissance" will be realized. they would have made a worthy contribution to building a solid foundation. As stated by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the inspiring idea of "From national revival to national rise" is entering our lives more and more deeply -21-.

On this basis, we are taking important steps to fundamentally improve the lives of our people, ensure human rights and freedoms, the rule of law and social justice, and innovative development[1,2]". It is our good intentions and great goals that every citizen of the new Uzbekistan, which is taking important steps in the field of innovative development, will study the history of our motherland free of objective and ideological views from scientific research works based on innovative approaches and use the results of such research in history education. reality - they would have made a worthy contribution to building a solid foundation of the "Third Renaissance". "Today, when talking about our country, the phrase "New Uzbekistan" is mentioned. This is a recognition of the fact that we have stepped into a completely new stage of development in recent years, and of our great achievements [2,3]", said the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan,

Shavkat Mirziyoyev. We use the results of archaeological excavations, examples of local written literature (for example, "Avesta", old Iranian inscriptions, sources written by Greek, Chinese, Indian and other local authors) to illuminate the most ancient historical periods of the Uzbek statehood. Of course, in this regard, we use scientific and logical methods, such as comparative study, laws of historical and cultural development, remembering traditions. At the beginning of the 1st millennium BC, our ancestors learned to process iron.

Therefore, a wide path has been opened for the improvement of labor tools, which are the impetus for any development. This, in turn, caused the expansion and acceleration of human activity. This situation is considered to be one of the main factors that motivates relevant quality changes in all spheres of society: political, social, cultural, economic, international relations. It is known that huge artificial irrigation systems were operating in Khorezm as early as VII-VI centuries BC[3,68]. The fact that artificial irrigation works were so important -22- testifies to the place of agriculture in the life of our ancestors. In fact, scientists have proved that during those times such fields as cultivation of grain, oil-bearing plants, policing, horticulture were developed. As for the social relations of this period, the Avesta (VIII-VII centuries BC) mentions such social classes as priests, soldiers, farmers, and artisans.

When we want to consider the state policy and management system of the time of Amir Temur and the Timurids, it is extremely important to mention that the essence of the state and statehood is the organization that creates various opportunities in a certain place and society for the benefit of the local people. After all, the foundations of the state, statehood, every society and nation are "made once". In this sense, Uzbek statehood started its history from the first half of the 1st millennium BC until Amir Temur came to the top of our country, and different dynasties (political parties in today's language) came to manage the path of development for almost 2100 years. Their activities took place in different

times and in different objective-subjective conditions. There are several reasons why we emphasize this issue. First, we look at common concepts such as the state of Amir Temur, the state of the Timurids. After all, the foundations of statehood will be the same. Therefore, if it is said that it is not Amir Temur's state, but the stage of Uzbek statehood led by Amir Temur, it is completely true. Secondly, the concept of the state of Amir Temur cuts off the path of development of our statehood, both before and after it, and after it (this idea also applies to other dynastic states, of course). On the one hand, it falsifies history, and on the other hand, it makes it difficult to understand the essence of the staged processes in the history of our statehood, for example, the era of Amir Temur.

After all, even from a purely scientific point of view, only when it is observed in the process of observation, there is a wave, an opportunity for a conclusion is created. -23- Thirdly, no matter how much we talk about the essence and possibilities of Uzbek statehood, if we do not witness its practical expression (and from today's point of view, its builder), it will remain just talk. In this sense, the era of Amir Temur is extremely important as it revealed the essence and scope of our statehood in practice (of course, in the conditions of his time). Thus, since the Uzbek statehood has passed the path of 2100 years of development until the time of Amir Temur, we can make the first conclusion accordingly. Amir Temur's era of statehood, the system was organized based on a specific past, traditions, experiences, lessons and laws.

A legitimate question arises here: what were the laws of the past, experiences, that is, the foundations of statehood reflected in, and how did Amir Temur treat them during the years when he was the leader of our country? It is very important to ask the question in this way. After all, in our understanding, the potential of a statesman and politician (and the resulting greatness) is determined, first of all, by how deeply he understands the principles of statehood and is able to follow them in practice. This is a very difficult task.

We will try to clarify the truths of Amir Temur regarding state management, statecraft and military policy. We said that the rule of Genghis Khan in the country had a negative impact on the development of all areas. The field of public administration is no exception. In general, the political worldview and education formed in nomadic conditions did not allow for the adoption of local management traditions for Genghis figures. For this reason, the centuries-old experience and traditions of the administration of statehood in the previous eras could not find their continuity in practice during the rule of Genghis Khan. If we consider that this period has passed a century and a half, it becomes clear how much the situation in this field has worsened.

One of Amir Temur's services to the Uzbek statehood is that, after a long period of 150 years, customs and traditions have existed for a long time, despite the fact that there have been major changes -24- Uzbek statehood was able to restore the classic examples of the management system (we would even call it science). In the end, he was able to solve this difficult task with wisdom. So, during the reign of Amir Temur, the administration was divided into two offices: dargah and devans (ministries). Dargah is the highest office. Its head is naturally the supreme ruler of the state. It is known that after Amir Temur came to the top of the state, he declared Suyurgatmish, one of the Genghis Khans, as the khan, that is, the supreme ruler[4,293].

At the same time, we know that Suyurgatmish was in the position of "false khan" and the actual power was at the disposal of Sahibgiron. The question arises why such a contradiction arose. We noted that the 150-year rule of Genghis had a great impact on the life of the country. Political relations, views, customs are one of the hottest areas of the society, which will be rich in qualitative innovations and changes. For example, let's take our great grandfather's camp in the desert. In our country, the residence of the head of state has been natural in the cities for centuries, but during the Genghis era, on the contrary, the khan should live in the

wilderness, the belief of his tribe was deeply embedded in the political environment. A number of similar changes have found their place in this half-century process. It's not about whether they are right or wrong. Importantly, when Amir Temur came to the top of the state, they formed the reality of society. The owner had no choice but to think of these things. On the other hand, in 1370, besides Amir Temur, there were several other powerful emirs and social and political forces supporting them. They secretly or openly intended to conduct independent politics, even to occupy the supreme throne.

In such circumstances, Amir Temur could not officially declare himself Khan. Because this was an excuse for the opponents and an incentive for protests and attacks. After all, according to the manner of those years, the political power should have been at the disposal of the Genghis family. On the third hand, since Suyurgatmish Khan ascended, the issue of Amir Husayn was not resolved, or rather, it was on the verge of being resolved. Amir Husayn officially declared Qabilshah (1364), then Adil Sultan -25- (1365) as Khan [5,114-260].

Therefore, the declaration of Suyurgatmish as khan by Amir Temur was considered equivalent to canceling the "khanate" of Adil Sultan, that is, the rule of Amir Husayn. So, based on the reality of that time, this issue was implemented in order to strengthen the power of Amir Temur. This was what was important for the owners at this time. List of used literature: 1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Independence is a source of strength for the realization of our noble intentions and great goals. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the ceremony dedicated to the twenty-ninth anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "New Uzbekistan", September 1, 2020 2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Independence is a source of strength for the realization of our noble intentions and great goals. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the twenty-ninth anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "New Uzbekistan", September 1, 2020 3. Gulomov Ya. Irrigation history of Khorezm,

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